

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ALLOCATION OF SEA AND RIVER CARRIERS' RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE CARRIAGE AND THE CARGO; IDENTIFICATION OF THE CARRIER UNDER CHARTER PARTY AND THE CARRIER UNDER BILL OF LADING; CARRIER UNDER CHAIN OF CHARTER PARTIES FOR HIRE OF VESSEL AND CARRIAGE OF GOODS BY SEA; CARRIERS AND SUBCARRIERS IN INTERMODAL LINER SERVICES

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Abstract

An important issue in the theory of private maritime law is the identification of maritime carriers. The issue of identification of carriers in water transport is complicated from a legal point of view. Complications on the issue arise from the responsibilities of carriers, which can be divided into 2 categories: responsibilities for performance of the transportation and responsibilities for the cargo. Thanks to the development of good commercial practices in shipping industry, maritime contractors who are not de facto shipowners can legally engage in the transport of goods as carriers. This is the reason to make distinction between maritime carriers under a contract of carriage (Charter Party) and maritime carriers under a transport document (Bill of Lading). When the contract of carriage is concluded between the shipowner and the actual shipper, then the shipowner assumes full responsibility for the carriage and the cargo. But in cases where there is a Chain of Charter Parties, then it is possible the responsibilities for the carriage and for the cargo to be divided between two legal entities - e.g. between shipowners and time charterers. Clarification of this issue is very important in the port of unloading, where the goods have to be handed over to the legal consignee, because when there has been found any irregularity on cargo regarding its' quantity and condition, then arises the question who should take the responsibility for the damaged or short delivered cargo.

Keywords: carrier; subcarrier; carriage; bills of lading issued by shipowners; bills of lading issued by time charterers; damages and claims for cargo; contracts for maritime transport services; charter party; carriers under chain of charter parties

1. Introduction

The rules governing the responsibilities of the maritime carrier are a central part of the international maritime conventions. They regulate the distribution of risks and the balance of rights and responsibilities between the carrier and cargo interests. In particular, they determine when and to what extent the carrier is liable for economic losses arising from damage to goods or delay in delivery occurring while the goods were in the carrier's custody.

The practice developed over time has witnessed an attempt to allocate risks between the carrier and cargo interests, both by charter party and by a bill of lading. In this regard, the article focuses on the international carriage of goods by sea. It does not address liability regimes for other international modes of transport. It compares the status of carriers based on the responsibilities arising from contractual relationships, assuming that they apply to the settlement of contracts for the international carriage of goods by sea.

The contract of carriage by sea is usually concluded by the charter party when one is concluded. When no written contract of carriage is concluded, the carrier issues only a bill of lading, which proves the existence of a contract of carriage and includes the main clauses of the contract. [3],[4] This practice in maritime

law has also led to the distinction between tramp shipping and liner shipping.

It is obvious that the cargo liability regime consists of complex legal issues relating to the obligations, responsibilities, and immunities of the parties involved. [8],[9] One of these items is transport documents. The scope of the article does not include discussion and analysis of transport documents. However, they can be mentioned. Liability covered is contractual liability only. Obligations of the carrier from sources other than contractual are not considered.

1.1. Parties to contracts for rendering maritime transport services:

- Assignors - divided into two categories:
 - Shippers (cargo traders) - who charter the vessel for transport of goods by sea,
 - Charterers - who hire the vessel for period of time
- Performers - divided into two categories:
 - Shipowners – who perform the carriage by their own vessel as Carriers,
 - Bareboat or Time Charterers – who sublet the vessel to other sub-charterers in order to perform the carriage of the goods as Carriers

The existing legal ways for trading in maritime transport services can be done by contracts of carriage

(charter parties), also by so-called Chain of Charter Parties. In cases where there is no Chain of Charter Parties, then the cargo has to be transported under a single contract of carriage (Voyage Charter Party or Liner Bill of Lading), which has to be concluded directly between the actual Shipowner and the Shipper (cargo trader). [2] In this case the shipowner is a carrier under the Charter Party, also a Carrier under cargo transport document (Bill of lading). The same situation is in the cases where the vessel is trading under Bareboat Charter. The Bareboat Charterer assumes full control and responsibility for the ship, that's why on a later stage should be considered as Carrier under the subsequent Contract of carriage for certain cargo, which is concluded between Bareboat Charterer (as carrier) and the Shipper of the goods, also then the Bareboat Charterer should assume the responsibility as Carrier under Bill of lading issued by the Master on behalf of the Bareboat Charterer of the performing vessel. It is a common practice during last 100 years to be used different trading patterns (Chains of Charter Parties). In these cases, the Carrier under the Contract of carriage with the End-charterer is not the actual Shipowner. From a legal point of view the Carrier under the Bill of lading must be the Shipowner or Bareboat Charterer, if the vessel trades under Bareboat Charter. But if the ship is chartered on Time Charter, then arise two options. In both options the Time Charterers are Carriers under the Contract of carriage (Voyage Charter Party and Liner Bill of Lading) with End-charterers, but the contracting parties of the Time Charter Party may agree the Time Charterers to assume also the responsibilities as Carriers under Bill of Lading, which is not obligatory but it is legally allowed.

1.2. Responsibilities of the carrier for the carriage and the cargo

• Responsibilities of the carriers for the voyage under the contract of carriage

The conditions for transport of the goods by sea are recorded in the current contract for sea transport (Charter Party). An exception is Liner Shipping where the conditions of carriage are recorded in the Liner Bill of Lading. One of the most important responsibilities of the Carriers is for the ship to arrive at the port of loading and to be ready for loading in all respects, within the agreed time, also to be seaworthy at the beginning of the voyage. After loading completion, the vessel must sail to the port of unloading at reasonable speed, without any deviation from the usual route, if weather permitting. Failure to comply with this obligation is a ground for the Shipper to terminate the contract and hire another ship, and respectively the Carrier of the canceled ship should pay compensation for the extra freight to the carrying ship, if it is higher than the first agreed freight.

• Responsibilities of the carriers for the cargo under the Bill of Lading

Responsibilities for the cargo begin at the moment of its' acceptance on board the ship, then it is stored by the crew during the voyage and finally handed over to the consignee of the cargo at the port of unloading. At the port of loading, the master of the ship de facto represents the consignees of the goods and should show

due diligence about the quantity and condition of the received goods for transportation. The master of the ship is obliged to deliver the goods at the port of unloading in same condition as it's noted in the Bill of Lading signed by the master. In case of claims in the port of unloading regarding the condition and quantity of the goods, then the carrier as per the Bill of Lading is liable to the consignee of the goods. In case of damage or lack of the goods, the Carrier under the Bill of Lading is responsible for compensating the damage.

1.3. Identification of the carrier by the Bill of Lading; signing of the Bill of Lading by Master

One of the very important issue is to determine whether the Bill of Lading is proof of a contract of carriage with the Shipowner or with the Time charterer as a carrier (under the Bill of Lading). Bills of Lading signed by the Master of the ship and not bearing the name of the Carrier shall be considered as Bills of Lading of the Shipowner. The name of the Carrier should be written on the top right, in the free field on the second page of the Bill of Lading. In case, where the name of the carrier is not written in the Bill of Lading, then the Shipowner is considered to be the Carrier. The parties to the Time Charter may agree that the Time Charterer should assume the responsibility as Carrier (under Bill of Lading) and then the name of the Time Charterer shall be written in the Bill of Lading accordingly. There is a legal possibility for the Master of the ship to sign the Bill of Lading on behalf of the Time Charterer, which is equivalent of writing the name of the Time Charterer as a Carrier in the Bill of Lading. Bareboat Charter (or Demise Charter) should be considered as a special case in this regard. The Demise Charterer is figuratively speaking "with the shipowner's shoes" and assumes his responsibilities, i.e. his name should be written as a Carrier in the Bill of Lading. In principle, Bareboat Charter agreements are registered with the flag organizations, which issue a new Temporary Registry Certificate for the ship, in which instead of the name of the Shipowner, the name of the Demise Charterer is written, which commits his responsibility for the ship and the cargo instead of that of shipowner. [1]

CONCLUSION: The Carrier who is responsible for the cargo under Bill of Lading is predetermined (agreed) in governing Charter Party. If the name of the carrier is not written in the blank field at the top right on page 2 of the Bill of Lading, then the carrier under the Bill of Lading is considered to be the Shipowner or Bareboat Charterer, if there is a governing Bareboat Charter. If the ship is sailing on a Time Charter, and the parties to the Time Charter Party agree that the Time Charterer will assume the responsibility as Carrier under Bill of Lading (which is optional), then Time Charterers' name should be recorded at top right side on page 2 of the Bill of Lading as Carrier.

2. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo under different types of charters

2.1. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo under Bareboat Charter agreements

In accordance to Bareboat Charter Parties, the ship is considered rather than as a technical facility, which once the crew has been assigned and all certificates of the flag and the classification organization have been

issued accordingly, it acquires the legal right to be considered as a vessel permitted to sail and perform transportation of cargo. That's why the owners of the ship may charter-out their ship without a crew (under Bareboat Charter), and the Charterers, after taking the ship, assume full responsibility for the ship including obligation to employ the crew and maintain the ship. The ship should be insured by Bareboat Charterers for the benefit of the Shipowner and the Bareboat Charterer, i.e. in case of total loss of the ship, then the insurance will be received by the Shipowner, but in case of damage to the ship, then the insurance will be received by the Bareboat Charterer in order to rectify the damages on the ship. Bareboat Charterers trades with the ship as a Shipowner (referred to in English Maritime law as a Disponent owner, respectively conclude Voyage Charters or operate the vessel Liner Trade. Under these contracts, the responsibility for the carriage and the cargo is on Bareboat Charterer.

2.2. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo in Time Charter Parties

In accordance to Time Charter Parties, shipowners assume the responsibility for crew employment and ship's technical maintenance. Time Charterer pays hire and in exchange receives the right to use the ship to transport their own cargo, also other charterer's cargo, but on his own expense, i.e. receives the right to operate and trade with the ship as Carriers. The Time Charterers transport cargoes their expenses by concluding Voyage Charters or issuing Liner Bills of Lading, i.e. become Charter Party Carrier. Who will be the Carrier on the Bill of Lading for the goods carried on the Voyage Charter or under liner Bill of Lading is agreed in the Time Charter Party - between the Shipowner and the Time Charter. If it is agreed in the Time Charter Party that the Carriers under the Bills of Lading would be the Time Charterers, then this should be recorded on the second page of the Bill of Lading, in the free field, at the top right. If it is agreed in the Time Charter that the Carriers under the Bills of Lading would be the Shipowners, then it is not obligatory the same to be recorded in the Bill of Lading. If the name of the Carrier is not written in the Bill of Lading, then the Carrier is considered to be the Shipowner as per Ship Registration Certificate by default. The ship's registration certificate shall be issued in the name of the Shipowner. When ships sails on the Bareboat Charter, then Temporary Certificates of Registration of the ship are issued in the name of the Bareboat Charterer. [10]

2.3. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo under Voyage Charter Party

In accordance to Voyage Charter Parties, the Carrier under contract for carriage may be the Shipowner or Bareboat Charterer or Time Charter or another charterer who has chartered the ship from one of the previous Carriers in the Chain of Charter Parties and who has concluded a fixture with End-charterer – that is so-called back to back Charter Party with the final Shipper. The Carrier of the Bill of Lading may be the Shipowner or the Bareboat Charterer or the Time Charterer, if this is agreed in the Time Charter. But if the Voyage Charterer has concluded another charter (back to back) with the final Shipper, cannot be a Carrier under a Bill of

Lading. [5]

2.4. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo in Liner Trade

In Liner Shipping trade are used Liner Bills of Lading where all terms and conditions of the carriage are incorporated accordingly. In this case the carrier may be the Shipowner or Bareboat charterer or Time charterer. Due to the Bill of Lading also has the function as Contract of carriage, the Carrier for the carriage and the cargo is the same. The special condition in Liner shipping is that the transportation is on liner terms, which include loading and unloading of the goods to be at the expense of the Carrier. Carriers take responsibility for the cargo when it is handed over by the consignor to the Agent of the Carrier, against which the consignor receives a Bill of Lading (so-called Received B/L) and thus the contract of carriage is formed. [6]

2.5. Carriers responsibilities for the carriage and the cargo in a Chain of Charter Parties: Bareboat Charter - Time Charter - Voyage Charter

This Chain of Contracts is considered as classic chain with real application when the ship is purchased on lease for investment purposes. Under this trading scheme, the new (future) shipowner hires the ship on a Bareboat Charter, with a purchase option, and then leases the ship. The Bareboat Charterer can hire a management company, which for a fixed fee to perform the technical maintenance of the ship, as well as the appointment and management of the crew. In this chain of charters, the Carrier on the Voyage Charter or Liner Bill of lading is the Time Charterer. In Time Charter parties should be agreed which of the parties will be the Carrier under Bill of Lading issued under the Voyage Charter.

3. Carriers identification in Chain of Charter Parties

At least two carriers are involved in the charter chain, the first of which is the carrier that has concluded the charter with the shipper (the end tenant - End-Charterer), and the subsequent carriers in the charter chain are subcontractors. Terminology has been adopted in the theory and practice of Europe's maritime and inland waterways, using different jurisdictions. Maritime transport is usually governed by English private maritime law, and inland waterway transport in Europe is governed by the Budapest Convention on Contracts for the Carriage of Goods by Inland Waterway (CMNI) of 3 October 2000.

No matter how many charter parties are in the chain, as well as the jurisdiction in which they are concluded, at both ends of the chain are always the shipowner and the shipper (as Principals), and between them are the carriers of the charter party chain. Carriers in the chain who are not the actual shipowners actually participate in two adjacent charter parties in the chain, and in the direction of the shipowner, they actually act as charterers of the ship, and in the direction of the shipowner, they are carriers.

❖ Definitions of carriers under English private maritime law

In English private Maritime Law and terminology,

instead of the term Carrier, Ship Owners or only Owners are used when they are the actual owners of the ship. Then when the carriers are not the actual owners of the ship, then they are called Disponent owners.

- Disponent owner is a "charter party carrier" with the respective charterer in the charter party chain. Any charterer who in turn charter-out or subcontracts the ship to another charterer is a 'Disponent owner' vis-à-vis the latter. The demise charter relinquishes the ship under Time Charter, to the Time Charterer; The Time Charterer of the ship concludes a contract of carriage with the voyage charterer. All act as Disponent owners. The demise charter is the Disponent owner on the time charter, with the time charterer; the Time Charterer is the Disponent owner on the Voyage Charterer, with the Voyage Charterer. The Voyage Charterer may also sublet the ship to another charterer, for whom he will also should be the Disponent owner. Only the last Charterer in this chain who does not sublet the ship to anyone else is the End-charterer or Actual Charterer. The last Charterer (end-charterer) may not know about the existing chain of carriers (Owners and Disponent Owners) and enters into a contract with the last Disponent owner with whom he concludes a charter. This last Disponent owner may be the Voyage Charterer of the previous Disponent owner, but is still considered the Disponent owner relative to the last tenant (end-charterer).

❖ Definitions for Carriers under the Budapest Convention on Contracts for the Carriage of Goods by Inland Waterways (CMNI) of 3 October 2000.

The Budapest Convention on Contracts for the Carriage of Goods by Inland Waterways (CMNI) of 3 October 2000 has been ratified by the Republic of Bulgaria and it is a part of European and Bulgarian legislation. In addition to the direct conclusion of contracts of carriage between shipowners and shippers, the Convention allows for the carriage of goods by more than one active charter party. This legal opportunity is used mainly by brokerage companies and freight forwarding companies, which are engaged in the entire transport of goods, performing the so-called door-to-door transportation.

- Contract of Carriage means any contract, regardless of its name, under which the carrier undertakes to transport goods by inland waterway against payment of freight.

- Carrier means any person with whom or on whose behalf the shipper has entered into a contract for the carriage of goods by inland waterway. The carrier is obliged to transport the cargo within the specified period and to the specified destination, handing it over to the consignee of the cargo, in the same condition in which it is loaded on the ship.

- Actual carrier means any person, other than an employee or agent of the carrier, to whom the carrier has entrusted the performance of the carriage in whole or in part. A contract between a carrier and an actual carrier is a contract of carriage within the meaning of the Convention. For the purposes of such a contract, all the provisions of the Convention relating to the shipper shall apply to the carrier. The rules applicable to the carrier shall apply to the performing carrier. [7]

CONCLUSION: Disponent owner and Carrier have the same meaning.

4. Maritime Sub-carriers in Liner Shipping using Intermodal Transport Units

Liner Shipping is under constant development in Intermodal Sector during recent 30-40 years. Generally speaking there are four modern types of Intermodal Transport Units (ITU). For this reason, the Shipping Lines invest in different types of vessel specially designed to make carriage of Intermodal units used to carry cargoes:

- Container vessels are designed for transportation of Containers which are globally used in deep sea and short sea carriages and they have a very big importance for international trade.

- Ro-Ro vessels are designed for transportation of Trucks and Trailers – they are usually used in short sea carriages to cross some seas where is convenient for line and when there is economical reason.

- Ferryboats are designed for transportation of Railway Wagons – their application is like the application of Ro-Ro vessels, but the Shipping lines with this type of vessels are not so much.

- Light Carriers (LASH system) are designed to carry Lighters (shallow draft non-propelled barges) which are used mainly to connect the deltas of 2 big navigable rivers with well developed economies of country where the rivers flows.

All this four types of vessels are designed to carry Intermodal Transport Units and for this reason they are placed on suitable shipping lines and employed as Sub-carriers to Intermodal Transport Operators who as carriers conclude Intermodal and Multimodal Transport Contracts with Shippers (cargo traders). Intermodal Transport Operators are carriers as per Contract of carriage, also under the Transport document (Bill of Lading as per Hague-Visby Rules (1968), Road Transport Document as per CIM, Railway Transport Document as per COTIF).

5. Conclusion

The article presents one of the ever-current topics in global maritime transport, namely, the carrier's responsibilities. As a scientific study, it also contributes to the detailed understanding of many high-profile issues in practice and theory.

The carrier's responsibilities can only be properly understood when one is aware of the contract of carriage and the documents that accompany it. However, in maritime law there are numerous documents with different names, such as charter party, bill of lading, booking note, etc. The carrier's responsibilities largely depends on the availability and good drafting of these documents.

The comparative analysis made in the article helps the gradual presentation of the described information and its more acceptable assimilation.

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